

Sustain Sahel

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Main Authors: Georg Cadisch (UHOH), Eric Koomson (UHOH), Carsten Marohn (UHOH, UKAS), Abdoul Aziz Diouf (CSE)

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Author(s)	Georg Cadisch (UHOH), Eric Koomson (UHOH), Carsten Marohn (UHOH, UKAS), Abdoul Aziz Diouf (CSE)
Editor	Harun Cicek (FiBL), Carla Pinho (FiBL)
Approved by	Harun Cicek (FiBL)
REA Project Officer	Alina KOZACENKO

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I. Executive summary

This work details the parameterization and calibration of the land use change impact assessment model (LUCIA) for the SustainSAHEL sites. This exercise utilized data from ongoing field measurement campaigns within SustainSAHEL, from associated projects, remote sensing and literature. Data used for parameterizing LUCIA ranged from spatial maps (e.g. land use/ cover, soil, DEM, LDD), plant and soil parameters, weather, management data. LUCIA has been parameterized for all the seven SustainSAHEL study sites. Detailed model calibration and evaluation in this work was initialised for Niakhar, using the Sob watershed where the Faidherbia flux site (WVP4) was resourceful in providing data for simulating and fine-tuning water and hydrological routines and below and aboveground processes related to plant growth and development.

A pixel level (30 m × 30 m area) calibration set up was used to derive a good fit between the measured and simulated parameters. Above ground biomass (AGB), grain yield, LAI of millet (*Pennisetum glaucum*) and groundnut (*Arachis hypogaea*) and Acacia (*Acacia albida*) were selected for detailed model calibration. Calibration of AGB and grain yield was based on a seasonal resolution by comparing simulated AGB and grain yield with measured AGB and grain yield at the end of the 2018, 2019 and 2020 cropping seasons. The performance of LUCIA in adequately representing measured field data was assessed using coefficient of determination (CD), root mean square error (RMSE) and the Nash–Sutcliffe model efficiency (Loague and Green, 1991; Nash and Sutcliffe, 1970).

The model adequately captured the observed AGB and grain yield of millet produced at maturity with EF value of 0.65 and 0.59 respectively. The AGB and grain yield was calibrated with RMSE of approximately 29.7 and 29.8 respectively. The parameterized model was used to run several sensitivity analyses on specific LUCIA parameters that can impact crop performance. The sensitivity analysis showed good simulated response of different levels of mineral and organic fertilization, and shrub residues of different quality. At the landscape-scale, LUCIA simulated the growth dynamics of different trees and shrubs at different contrasting times.

2. Introduction

This report is the second deliverable of WP7 (D7.2). It builds on the first report (D7.1), which provided a landscape characterization on the extent and suitability of crop, shrub and livestock (CSL) systems. Outputs from D7.1 also showed on a broader scale existing crops, cropping systems, soil types, land use and cover of trees and shrubs providing a baseline for LUCIA parameterization. The aim of this report is to provide an overview of a parameterized and calibrated LUCIA model. Niakhar watershed in Senegal was used as the experimental site for this activity. Niakhar watershed consists of 4 sub-catchments namely Diohine, Ngalagne_kop, Sanghaie and Sob. The Sob sub – catchment was used for detailed modelling activities as the presence of the IRD Faidherbia flux on this SustainSahel experimental site provided detailed historical data (2018-2020). Moreover, most published and literature data in relation to the objective of this task exists for this site compared to the other locations.

3. LUCIA model setup, data and parameterization

3.1 LUCIA model

The land use change impact assessment model (LUCIA) is a spatially explicit and grid-based plot and landscape model that runs on a daily time step. It was built to simulate the effects of changes in environmental conditions, caused by farmers' land use and management strategies or climate change, on the availability of and changes to ecosystem services (Figure 1). Its applications include plant productivity, soil fertility, nutrient cycling and degradation of watersheds regarding agriculture production as well as ecosystem services such as erosion protection, water provision and retention, and soil organic matter accumulation and decomposition (Marohn and Cadisch, 2011). LUCIA handles variable landscape size and pixel resolutions, which allows simulating agroforestry systems and savanna rangelands with their heterogeneity in soil, vegetation, and topography, as well as livestock herd mobility patterns from the LUCIA-LIVSIM coupled framework. Land use and management (e.g., tillage, planting design, pruning, mulching, fertilizer application, weeding), which affect soil surface cover, the water balance, nutrient cycles, and soil organic matter (SOM) fluxes are all simulated in LUCIA in a spatially distributed way. Thus, these factors influence plant growth at the pixel scale, where different plant species (e.g. crops, trees, shrubs and grasses) can compete for soil-borne resources and light, depending on root and canopy architectures (Marohn and Cadisch, 2011; Marohn et al., 2013).

Figure 1. Diagrammatic representation of modules and application of LUCIA model

The plant growth module in LUCIA is based on the WOWorld FOod STudies (WOFOST, Supit, 2003) concept, and can simulate plant growth-soil-water interactions in rotations and intercropping systems (Figure 2). Tree growth simulation is adapted from the concepts in WaLNUCAS model (Noordwijk and Lusiana, 1999). The water balance (infiltration) module is built on KINEROS 2 (Woolhiser et al., 1990), while the soil erosion module is based on the Rose concept of soil erosion (Rose et al., 2007), which considers runoff entrainment-driven soil erosion dominant over rainfall-induced soil detachment (Noordwijk et al., 2011; Marohn et al., 2013; Lippe et al., 2014; Liu et al., 2018). Decomposition rates of

litter and SOM pools and flows are defined following the CENTURY approach (Parton et al. 1986). LUCIA is written in the PCRaster modeling language (van Deursen 1995), which builds on the Geographic Resources Analysis Support System (GRASS) mapcalc algorithms (Shapiro and Westervelt 1992), and combines GIS functions with a simple high level modeling language. PCRaster also contains specialized routing algorithms to simulate matter flows between pixels, making it optimized for dynamic watershed modeling.

Figure 2. Overview of modules and landscape-scale interactions in LUCIA model

3.2 Baseline data preparation and parameterization

LUCIA requires spatial maps, plant and soil parameters, weather, management and animal parameters. Inclusion of animal parameters will depend on whether LUCIA is coupled to LIVSIM or not. Detailed description of each data parameter requirement and preparation is discussed below.

3.2.1 Spatial maps

LUCIA (<https://lucia.uni-hohenheim.de>) requires spatial maps namely land use map, soil type map, area map, digital elevation model (DEM) and local drain direction (LDD) map as core inputs for spatially explicit simulation. All the spatial maps were acquired from global geospatial databases, which are freely available online. The Sob hydrological catchments, which includes plots used by other work packages (WP2, 4 and 5) for their field experiments and farmer fields, were delineated. DEM was accessed from National Aeronautics and Space Administrator–United States Geological Survey (NASA-USGS) as geo-referenced datasets. Based on the DEM, slopes and LDD corresponding maps were calculated using PCRaster software (<https://pccraster.geo.uu.nl/>). Land use and cover map was developed for the watershed by geo-referencing of major land use and vegetation and linked to remote sensing project data (WP7). Recently

available land cover maps were accessed from Water Productivity Open-access portal (WaPOR 2.1) and classified based on LANDSAT data. Soil map was extracted from International Soil Reference and Information Centre (ISRIC) at a 250 m resolution. In addition, 30 m resolution datasets of soil properties were retrieved from ISDA (Innovative Solutions for Decision Agriculture Ltd). Soil samples have also been collected along transects to validate this remotely sensed soil database. All the maps (Figure 3) were converted to 30 m pixel resolution to account for spatial heterogeneity as required for landscape scale modelling under smallholder's conditions.

Figure 3. Spatial map of Sob watershed showing Digital elevation model (DEM) (left) and soil map (right)

3.2.2 Plant parameters

Parameters related to plant growth of crops, trees and shrubs e.g. above ground biomass (AGB) and grain yield, biomass assimilates and plant partitioning at flowering and maturity, plant NPK content and plant quality (lignin and polyphenol) of different shoots (leaf, stem, root and seed) at flowering and maturity etc. were obtained by field investigation and subsequently analyzed and manually entered in LUCIA. Additional data were taken from default databases provided by LUCIA, existing validated models e.g. World Food Studies (WOFOST) and literature. To initialize the growth estimation of woody biomass, LUCIA uses allometric and other empirical equations. Data on tree allometry such as diameter at breast height (DBH), tree height, basal circumference, canopy diameter, and branch numbers, which drive allometric relationships were obtained from literature and partners (Wp5 and 6).

3.2.3 Land use maps

Land use and cover maps have been developed for all the study sites in the SustainSAHEL project by the Centre de Suivi Ecologique (CSE) following geospatial data acquisition (accessed from Water Productivity

Open-access portal (WaPOR 2.1)), processing and mapping (Ndao et. al., 2019). This approach is based on remote sensing, object-based segmentation, spatial analysis and unsupervised classification in order to account for the landscape spatial heterogeneity in different plant types from annual crops to perennial trees of natural forests to agroforestry systems and rangelands. The resulting land use maps were delineated for specific watersheds or landscapes where modelling activities are applied. Processed land use maps in GIS formats are exported as ASCII files and processed into PCRaster formats for LUCIA iterative user interface (Figure 4).

Figure 4. Land use map of Sob watershed

3.2.4 Soil parameters

The main measured soil input parameters for LUCIA were soil thickness defined for the generic soil horizon (see Table I in appendix), texture (sand, silt and clay), soil organic carbon (Corg), total nitrogen (Nt), mineralized nitrogen (Nmin), total P, available K, pH. Soil profile data from Sob at the Faidherbia flux site (WP5) was used for the pixel level simulation. At the landscape, we extracted similar data from ISDA at a 30 m resolution for all existing soil types in the Sob watershed. Other soil parameters were derived using pedo transfer functions in LUCIA e.g. bulk density, saturated hydraulic conductivity, total pore volume and volumetric water content at field capacity and permanent wilting point.

3.2.5 Meteorological parameters

Input climate data for LUCIA are rainfall, air and soil temperature, solar radiation and evapotranspiration. These data were obtained from:

1) Faidherbia-Flux (Niakhar-Sob): the Faidherbia-Flux station is operated by IRD, France and equipped with eddy covariance antennas designed to monitor radiation, energy and GHG fluxes over the whole

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ecosystem, and fluxes below tree crowns (from soil and crops). Meteorological data was provided by an automatic station (CR1000, Campbell Sci.) equipped with classical sensors. Measured parameters included air temperature and relative humidity (CS215, 2 m), wind speed (WindMaster sonic anemometer (Gill Instruments, Lymington, UK), 4.5 m and estimation at 2 m) and rainfall (TE25MM) (Diongue et al., 2022). Recordings of climate data from the Faidherbia–Flux were averaged to obtain representative daily data for three years (2018–2020). We very much appreciate the provision of the data this calibration activity by Dr. Roupsard (IRD) and his colleagues.

2) Own (WP6 and 7) meteorological stations have been installed at all study sites where most of the SustainSAHEL interventions and farmer–level activities are ongoing. The rainfall-measuring device comprised of a tipping bucket rain gauge (MD532–HOBO, UP GmbH, Germany) connected to a logger (HOBO–UA 003–64 Pendant, Onset Computer corp., USA). The other devices comprising of a HOBO pro v2 relative humidity/air temperature sensor, and an RT–I soil temperature sensor were connected to a data logger (Decagon EM50). Additionally, a connected HOBO MX Temp/light measures PAR photon flux, which is converted to total solar radiation.

3.2.6 Management data

Management data of cropping systems and field activities were obtained from field visits, cropping calendar of ongoing field research by partners and from literature. For instance, Eric Koomson visited Koulikoro, Niakhar, Ouarkhokh, Yilou and Saria in June 2022, and Georg Cadisch in September 2022 visited and participated in innovation platform activities in Ouarkhokh, Niakhar and Saria to gain understanding of ongoing farmer dissemination activities, impacts and challenges facing implementation of activities. Overall, management related data included in LUCIA comprised: ploughing dates (if applicable), planting patterns (distances within and between rows), fertilizer application dates, amounts of elemental N, P, K, manure application dates and amounts, C, N, P, K content of the manure, pruning dates and proportions of leaves and stems that are pruned and that remains in the field as mulch, flowering and harvest dates etc.

3.3. Model improvements

a) Multilayer soils

In its original version, LUCIA allowed the parameterization of two soil horizons only. In order to more adequately represent water and nutrient availability and movements in the soil profile in dryland areas new python routines in the main script (lucia.py) have been added to allow for any user defined layer numbers and thickness (cm). Corresponding input file formats have been created for soil properties (soil.lut), initial surface and soil litter (litterini.lut), and soil organic matter fractions (lusom.lut) to allow user external parameterisation.

b) Improved soil water and leaching routine

Further improvements in soil water movement and leaching were included according to the LeachA concept of Hutson and Wagnet (1993). In this approach the traditionally used ‘tipping bucket’ concept many crop models use was extended by a capacity model in which soil water is divided into mobile and immobile phases (Figure 5). The division between mobile/immobile water is assumed to be the water content corresponding to a defined matric potential, e.g. from -1000 to -200 kPa. After rainfall, percolation (infiltration) of water and dissolved solutes (e.g. nutrients) is allowed in the mobile phase only. After removing evapotranspiration and plant water uptake, equilibration between adjacent segments is driven by differences in water content rather than water potential, and mobile and immobile phases within

segments are assumed to reach equilibrium each day. This allows an improved description of percolation/leaching processes and is closer to a full mechanistic approach as used in specialized models using the Richard equation.

Figure 5: Comparison of simple tipping bucket water movement concept (left) with the improved LeachA (right) approach as suggest by Hutson and Wagnet (1993).

3.4. Sob watershed

The Sob watershed in the Niakhar region, a groundnut basin of Senegal, was used to parameterize the LUCIA model. The elevation of Sob ranges from -5 to 20 m a.s.l. The climate is Sudano-Sahelian, with a wet season from June to October, followed by a dry season from November to May (Roupsard et al., 2020). Annual rainfall is mono-modal, and varied between 453 and 599 mm during the simulation period from 2018 to 2020 respectively. Dominant soil groups were Arenosols and Gleysols. At the highly instrumented Faidherbia-Flux site (<https://ped.info/wikiObsSN/?Faidherbia-Flux>) in the agroforestry parklands, the soils are mainly loamy sand in texture. At the landscape, natural *Faidherbia albida* vegetation dominates rainfed crops of annual rotation of pearl millet (*Pennisetum glaucum*, var. Souna) and groundnut (*Arachis hypogaea*) (Roupsard et al., 1999).

3.4.1 Model calibration and uncertainty analysis

A pixel level (30 m × 30 m area) calibration was used to derive a good fit between the measured and simulated parameters. Aboveground biomass (AGB) and grain yield of millet were selected for model calibration. Calibration of AGB and grain yield was based on seasonal resolution by comparing simulated AGB and grain yield with measured AGB and grain yield at the end of each cropping season.

Additionally, we conducted a sensitivity analysis to evaluate the output of LUCIA model for plausibility by varying the input parameters assumed highly influential towards the outputs of LUCIA functions. Input parameters considered in this task comprised different N-mineral fertilizer amounts, soil amendments e.g. organic manure at different rates, shrub residue application e.g. *Guiera senegalensis* and *Piliostigma reticulatum* (varying lignin: polyphenol) and amounts, and their impacts on AGB and grain yield of millet and groundnut.

3.4.2 Statistical evaluation

The performance of the model in adequately representing measured field data was assessed using the Nash–Sutcliffe model efficiency (EF), coefficient of determination (CD) and root mean square error (RMSE) (Loague and Green, 1991; Nash and Sutcliffe, 1970). The EF indicates how good the model simulations are. An EF of 1 signifies a perfect 1:1 relationship between the simulated and observed values, and $EF < 0$ is an indication that the observed mean is a better estimate than the simulated outputs. The model is regarded as good fit if $EF > 75$, and $0.36 < EF < 0.75$ as acceptable (Moriasi et al., 2007). Studies by Pansak et al. (2010) and Lippe et al. (2014) used an EF threshold of > 0.6 as minimum performance benchmark during LUCIA and ERODEP calibrations. The RMSE measures the error associated with the simulated values. RMSE value of zero indicates a perfect simulation or fit, and smaller RMSE values signifies how closer simulated values are to the observed (Hussein et al., 2007). CD measures the proportion of the variance of observed data explained by the predicted data. CD value of 1 indicates a perfect prediction fit. We used CD values between 0.5 and 2 to evaluate the success of our model calibration.

$$EF = \frac{\sum_{i=1}^n (O_i - \bar{O})^2 - \sum_{i=1}^n (P_i - O_i)^2}{\sum_{i=1}^n (O_i - \bar{O})^2} \quad [Eq1]$$

$$CD = \frac{\sum_{i=1}^n (O_i - \bar{O})^2}{\sum_{i=1}^n (P_i - \bar{O})^2} \quad [Eq2]$$

$$RMSE = \left(\frac{\sum_{i=1}^n (P_i - \bar{O}_i)^2}{n} \right)^{0.5} \cdot \frac{100}{\bar{O}} \quad [Eq3]$$

Where n is the number of samples, \bar{O} mean of the observed data, P_i , predicted and O_i observed.

3.5 Results

3.5.1 Model evaluation in predicting crop AGB and grain yield

The performance of LUCIA model in predicting AGB and grain yield for Millet was assessed using EF and CD shown in Figure 6 below. Despite the few data available, the model showed reasonable acceptability for prediction with an EF of 0.65 and 0.59 for AGB and grain yield respectively in the calibration phase, the model fulfilled the performance benchmark (>0.6) used by Pansak et al. (2010) for WaNuLCAS and by Lippe et al. (2014) for Lucia-Erodep. The CD values were, however, low (0.32 and 0.23) and not between the 0.5 and 2 threshold that Liu et al. (2020) used for the successful calibration of the LUCIA model. With the increasing availability of measured AGB and grain yield data points during the ongoing project evaluation model performance is likely to improve in future calibration/validation evaluation processes.

Figure 6. Model performance of millet under agroforestry systems: a) AGB of millet; b) grain yield of millet.

3.5.2 Analysis of constraints

The simulation suggested that millet suffered from water stress (water stress indicator (water availability / water demand) towards 0) mainly at the beginning of the cropping season when its root system was not yet fully developed (Figure 7). This was more pronounced during dry years in 2018 and 2019, which received only 453 and 513 mm rain respectively compared to 599 mm rain in 2020. Groundnut appeared to be water stressed throughout its growth cycle for all three simulated cropping seasons, due to its lower simulated rooting depth. Further data on root depth development would support the fine tuning of water stress experienced by the crops in future.

Simulated N stress was mostly observed under millet. N stress signal was minimal at the beginning of each cropping season, but became strong and more pronounced at the end of the cropping season when increasing demand outweighed plant available N due to the low soil fertility and low N fertilization (50 kg

ha⁻¹ applied as NPK) (Figure 8). Simulated N stress under groundnut was minimal, due to supply of its N demand from biological N fixation, which was parameterized to provide 60% of its N demand.

Simulated P stress was similar to N mostly for millet. Under groundnut, a strong P limitation was observed during the latter part of the 2020 cropping season partly exacerbated due to the lower simulated rooting depth (Figure 9). Nutrient stress tended to be higher during wetter 2020 season which promoted a stronger crop growth and hence demand.

Figure 7. Simulated water stress by LUCIA model under millet and groundnut for baseline (BL) in 2018, 2019 and 2020 cropping season. Relative water stress is calculated as plant water supply over demand with 0 indicating maximum stress and 1 full supply. Rainfall is plotted as grey columns.

Figure 8. Simulated nitrogen (N) stress by LUCIA model under millet and groundnut for baseline (BL) in 2018, 2019 and 2020 cropping season. Relative N stress is calculated as plant water supply over demand with 0 indicating maximum stress and 1 full supply.

Figure 9. Simulated phosphorus (P) stress by LUCIA model under millet and groundnut for baseline (BL) in 2018, 2019 and 2020 cropping season. Relative P stress is calculated as plant water supply over demand with 0 indicating maximum stress and 1 full supply.

3.5.3 Uncertainty analyses

Results of uncertainty analysis of different mineral N fertilization, soil amendments e.g. organic manure at different rates, shrub residue application e.g. *Guiera senegalensis* and *Piliostigma reticulatum* (varying lignin: polyphenol) and amounts, and their impacts on AGB, and grain yield of millet and groundnut is shown and discussed in the next sections.

3.5.3.1 Different N mineral fertilization rates

Simulated AGB and grain yield of Millet increased with increasing N fertilization amounts (Figure 10). The 2020 cropping season showed the highest AGB and grain yield, which also corresponded with the year with the highest rainfall among the three simulated years. Although a higher cumulative rainfall was accrued during 2019 compared to 2018, its AGB and grain yield were relatedly lower compared to 2018. This could be due to timing of planting as planting at the first rain, as practiced in this region, could lead to poor crop performance if the subsequent rains delay. Simulations suggested relative large amounts of N seemed to be required to significantly boost millet performance; this could be due to the relatively high leaching losses occurring in these very sandy (>80 %) and the associated simulated poor N fertilizer use efficiency.

Figure 10. Simulated AGB and grain yield of Millet under different mineral – N fertilizer levels during 2018, 2019 and 2020 cropping season.

3.5.3.2 Different organic manure fertilization rates

Simulated AGB and grain yield of Groundnut also showed increasing trends under increasing cow dung manure amounts (Figure 11). The increase from one level to another was gradual as hypothesized and

observed during the 2019 and 2020 season. In 2018, there was a sharp increase in AGB and grain yield from 1 to 2.5 Mg ha⁻¹ manure application level. The simulations showed low rooting depth (14 cm) for 0 and 1 Mg ha⁻¹ manure rate, which restricted nutrient extraction in lower soil depths. Simulated AGB and grain yield of Groundnut followed a similar seasonal trend as observed for Millet under different N fertilizer amounts (2019<2018<<2020).

Figure 11. Simulated AGB and grain yield of Groundnut under different Cow dung manure levels during 2018, 2019 and 2020 cropping season.

3.5.3.3 Application of shrub residues (*Guiera senegalensis* and *Piliostigma reticulatum*)

For these simulations the following residue quality were utilized: N = 1.6/1.8 %, Lignin = 10.3/13.1 % and Polyphenols = 6.4/5.3 % for *Guiera* and *Piliostigma* respectively.

Simulated Millet AGB and grain yield showed increasing performance trends with increasing amounts of *Guiera* and *Piliostigma*, particularly during 2019 and 2020 cropping seasons (Figure 12). Millet performance under no soil amendment showed relatively higher AGB and grain yield than under 1 Mg ha⁻¹ amendment during 2018 season under both *Guiera* and *Piliostigma* amendment. Plant residues of *Piliostigma* performed slightly better than those of *Guiera*; this could be explained by the higher quality (e.g. higher N). In the current model, set up the effect of polyphenols was not yet implemented and hence the model could not account for it. However, future versions will include impact of polyphenols based on the results of the incubation studies of the MSc/PhD students in the project (WP5, 6).

Figure 12. Simulated AGB and grain yield of Millet under different levels of *Guiera senegalensis* and *Piliostigma reticulatum* leaf residues during 2018, 2019 and 2020 cropping season.

3.5.4 Shrub and tree parameterization

Parameterisation/calibration files have been created for the following shrubs and trees shown in Table I below. These files together with crops files (Millet and Groundnut) are available on the SustainSahel sharepoint for internal project use.

Table I. List of parameterized/ calibrated shrubs and trees for Niakhar region.

Nr.	Vegetation	Type	File format
1	<i>Guiera senegalensis</i>	Shrub	[xx.land]
2	<i>Piliostigma reticulatum</i>	Shrub	[xx.land]
3	<i>Faidherbia albida</i>	Tree	[xx.land]
4	<i>Acacia Senegal</i>	Tree	[xx.land]
5	<i>Adansonia digitata</i>	Tree	[xx.land]
6	Natural grassland	Grass	[xx.land]

3.5.5 Landscape growth dynamics

The parametrised shrubs and trees (Table 2) were simulated at the landscape level for their aboveground biomass (AGB) growth dynamics for one year (Figure 13). The vegetation (*Faidherbia albida*) selected by a cross showed a comparative growth in AGB from 16.9 Mg ha⁻¹ (day 1) to 7.6 Mg ha⁻¹ day on day 195 and approximately 14 Mg ha⁻¹ on day 339. The next step of this exercise will account for simulating the individual vegetation at different landscape positions to elicit their impact on for instance, different soils, topography, suitability of survival, and their impact on intercropping crop species.

Figure 13. Simulated land use performance in the Sob watershed resulting from changes in aboveground biomass (AGB) at day 1, 195 and 339 of the year.

3.5.6 Soil water dynamics

The new improved LUCIA version based on the LeachA concept (Hutson and Wagnet 1993) was used to simulate topsoil moisture content on an Acrisol from Rongo County, Western Kenya during the 2016 long rains cropping season for which measured soil moisture data were available (Figure 14). LUCIA simulation under LeachA captured and matched the observed soil moisture dynamics well. Simulated soil moisture under the traditional tipping bucket often overestimated soil water content compared to the observed, although the general dynamics was also well captured. Simulations using data from the Faidherbia-Flux site suggested similar good performance for the top soil layers.

Figure 14. Simulated and observed soil moisture content

4. Conclusion and outlook

Deliverable 7.2 provides an overview of a parameterized and calibrated improved version of LUCIA at the plot and landscape scale using Niakhar (Sob watershed) as case study. Large datasets spanning from spatial maps, soil, plant, land use and cover map, climate and management served as core input data for LUCIA. These data were acquired from SustainSahel WP partners working jointly on the field, own installed sensors, field visits, associated partners (IRD), literature and from existing model datasets e.g. WOFOST. This allowed a rigorous testing of individual processes running at the plant, soil and environmental interface, which further supported the improvement of multilayer soil functioning and soil, water and nutrient leaching routines.

The evaluation of LUCIA's performance in simulating AGB and grain yield of Millet and Groundnut revealed that the model showed reasonable acceptability for prediction. Data from subsequent years and the extension of LUCIA to the remaining study sites could further increase the robustness and overall performance of LUCIA considering the different systems. The sensitivity analysis further showed that LUCIA can simulate the responses of different levels of mineral and organic fertilization, and shrub residues of different quality well. At the landscape, LUCIA was set up to simulate the growth dynamics of different trees and shrubs. Detailed simulation of individual trees and shrubs at different landscape positions and their impact on intercropping crop species will be taken into account in the version of the next report. Corresponding resource files are available on the SustainSahel share point for project use.

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